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Multi-actor Network to Boost Short Food Supply Chains Across Europe

Join us for the SFS Innovation Platform Event!

MEMBER'S
EVENT

ONLINE

FREE
EVENT

The future of knowledge
sharing platforms at European
level

SUSTAINABLE FOOD SYSTEM
INNOVATION PLATFORM

05 June 2025
10:00 - 11:30 CEST

“The future of knowledge sharing platforms at a European level”

We are delighted to invite you to an upcoming online event hosted by the SFS Innovation Platform on Thursday, **5 June, from 10:00 to 11:30 AM (CET)**.

and Wasteless, **is a free, open-access online space designed to connect actors across Europe's agri-food and research ecosystems.** It supports knowledge sharing, collaboration, and innovation around sustainable farming and food systems.

This event will explore the evolving role of knowledge-sharing platforms in the European research and innovation landscape, featuring insights from experts and opportunities for audience interaction.

[Check the agenda and Register!](#)

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